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Risk Assessment

Risk assessment of smoked fish

Inspections and analyses in Italy and Switzerland

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INTRODUCTION

For thousands of years, smoking has been an efficient and cost-effective preservation and flavoring process for food particularly for fish.

In addition to the classic types of fish (salmon, herring and mackerel), trout has recently proven itself as a culinary alternative and has gained market share accordingly.

In mountain areas such as South Tyrol and Switzerland, where crystal clear water is available everywhere, this has led to the emergence of ever more small fish farms and smoking facilities. At the same time, interest in food safety has grown, as it is well known that the consumption of smoked products is associated with certain microbiological risks. There are many health benefits accrued to the dietary intake of fish, nevertheless, they possess a complex system that allows the bioaccumulation of heavy metals (Oyekunle et al., 2020). At low concentrations, some heavy metals are essential for many biological processes and enzymatic activities (Kumolu et al., 2009): iron, cobalt, copper, manganese, molybdenum, and zinc are required by humans (Lane and Morel, 2000). But at higher concentrations all metals are toxic and excessive levels can be damaging to the organism (Chronopoulos et al., 1997; Singh et al., 2011). Not only the raw material can expose the consumer to chemical risk, but also the treatments it undergoes, such as the smoking process. Smoking is mainly applied for its effects on the organoleptic profile of food. However, it provides undesirable effects due to the production process, during wood combustion of phenol, formaldehyde, organic acids, and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) (Ekomy et al., 2013).

To study the effects of smoking plants, the authors decided to conduct a comparative study in collaboration with the South Tyrol Veterinary Service, the Swiss Federal Food Safety and Veterinary Office and the Swiss Cantonal Office for Food Safety of the canton of Vaud (OFCO).

As part of this project, a total of 4 fish smoking plants in South Tyrol and 6 in Switzerland have been controlled (fig. 1; fig. 2).

Figure 1. Map of South Tyrol: the 4 smoking plants

Figure 2. Map of Switzerland with Canton Vaud (in red) where the smoking plants are located (source: Wikipedia, 2021)

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Italy

During inspection, the production process was examined in each company. The individual HACCP plans were critically assessed (especially the applied risk analysis) and an additional 300 g of vacuum-packed smoked trout fillets were sampled. Laboratory analyses were carried out to assess the microbiological and chemical contamination of smoked trout fillets.

Switzerland

6 plants (artisanal fisheries and supermarket fish shops) that produce smoked fish (cuts, smoked) were inspected in the canton of Vaud in the same way as in Italy.

In 5 inspected establishments, samples were taken at the end of production. In addition, 26 other samples were also taken in shops on sail of the Vaud market. In total, 46 samples were taken for subsequent analysis. Species other than trout were included in the Swiss study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION - ITALY

The production process consolidated from tradition, was almost similar in all companies: gutted fish are placed in brine and, after drying, hot-smoked in the oven; after cooling in the cold store, the fish are filleted and packaged; finally, labeling and shipping take place (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Flow diagram smoked trout

Not only the in-house recipe, but also differences in the various stages of production give this artisanal process its own character and play a decisive role in taste.

All 4 controlled smoking plants are family businesses and consist of 1 to 2 employees who are involved in the production process. The turnover per year varies between 1 and 2 tons and even increases to 20 tons with 2 companies. The smoked trout are given directly to the end consumer, sold at markets or in retail outlets, but also to wholesalers.

Two of the above-mentioned establishments slaughter and cut the fish themselves, while the other two are supplied with fish that have already been gutted. Frozen raw materials are not used. We were also able to establish big differences in the time the trout are soaked in the brine, which varies from 24 h to 48 h and can even last up to 72 h. Afterwards, the trout are cleaned individually with drinking water to remove the leach residue. Furthermore we observed large variations in temperatures and time spans during the subsequent drying of the fish. For example, one farm dries the fish at room temperature for about ½ hour, whereas another prefers drying at 40°C for 3 hours. The differences are due to different experiences and seasonal weather conditions, which strongly influence the humidity. Hot smoking is carried out at all 4 farms with natural beech chips (HACCP controlled) in a smoking chamber or a smoking oven. The trout, which are hung on hooks, remain in the smokehouse for 20 minutes to 2 ½ hours, depending on the temperature, which varies between 80°C and 110°C. The detected hot smoking temperatures match those reported in FAO guidelines (Guide to small scale trout processing methods, 2012). Here, too, we found differences in temperature and

time among the farms. In all 4 establishments, the core temperature of the fish is measured at random, which is between 66°C and 95°C. In the next step, the fish are filleted by hand on a clean surface and then immediately vacuum-packed and stored in a cool place at 0 to 2°C. The shelf life of the finished product is set at 14 days for two of the farms, 30 days for another and 5 weeks for the fourth. In order to guarantee the food safety and to avoid or minimize hygienic hazards, all 4 businesses make sure that the raw material (fish) comes from certified or recognized businesses. As registered smokehouses, they are obliged to draw up and adhere to an HACCP concept, which also includes a self-monitoring plan with regular microbiological examinations of the finished product as well as the working surfaces and the water. Three of the four farms are EU-approved because they supply to wholesalers and retailers.

Within the scope of the laboratory analyses, the following parameters were examined.

Water activity (Aw) and pH-value (by inductively coupled plasma spectrometry)

The water activity, which influences the microbiological, chemical and enzymatic stability of a product, showed a value ranging between 0.973 and 0.979 in all 4 farms. This indicates a perishable food. The pH value is in the slightly acidic range of 6.16 to 6.35.

Metals and salts

Arsenic, cadmium, mercury and lead were tested. Arsenic was detected in the trout fillets at all 4 farms. (The values showed residue of 0.110 mg/kg to 0.610 mg/kg). These results almost match those reported by Cieřlik et al., 2018. Cadmium could not be found in any of the fish. Mercury, on the other hand, showed values ranging between 0.009 mg/kg and 0.034 mg/kg (limit 0.50 mg/kg) in all fillets. The measured values do not exceed the maximum level set by Reg. CE 1881/2006. Reported results from other authors range for smoked trout between 0.02 mg/kg (Tkaczewska and Migdal, 2012) and 0.05 mg/kg (Cieřlik et al., 2018). Lead was detected in the sample of one establishment: the detected level of 0.071 mg/kg does not exceed the maximum level of 0.3 mg/kg (Reg. CE 1881/2006).

Sodium levels ranged from 0.658 g/100g to 0.898 g/100g. Salt in the form of sodium chloride was detectable and ranged between 1.46 g/100g and 2.25 g/100g.

Metals (in ICP) mg/kg	1	2	3¹	4¹
Arsenic As	0.120	0.711	0.110 0.156	0.142 0.610
Cadmium Cd	-	-	-	-
Mercury Hg	0.012	0.034	0.012 0.015	0.016 0.009
Lead Pb	-	0.071	-	-

Table 1. Residues of metals. 3¹ and 4¹: 2 values because of 2 different batch numbers

Chemical residues (disinfectants, pesticides, biocides)

Residues of benzyldimethyltetradecylammonium chloride (0.022 mg/kg, 0.043 mg/kg and 0.11 mg/kg) were found in fish fillets from 3 farms. benzyldimethylhexadecylammonium chloride was also detected in one sample. Both are used in the disinfection of surfaces. The presence of these chemical residues in the fish fillets could be related to the improper disinfection method used by the operators or to incorrect compliance with the instructions for use. Subsequent rinsing of the surfaces with drinking water should avoid this problem.

Chemical residues in mg/kg	1	2	3	4
Benzyldimethylhexadecylammonium chloride (BAC-16)	-	0.033	-	-
Benzyldimethyltetradecylammonium chloride (BAC-14)	0.022	0.043	-	0.11

Table 2. Chemical residues (-: value = 0)

Artificial colorants

No artificial colorants (E129, E123, E122, E124, E127, E132, E110, and E128) were detected in any of the trout fillets tested.

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons

Residues of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons were found in 2 farms. These were benzoanthracene (0.25 µg/kg, 0.95µg/kg), chrysene (0.95 µg/kg, 0.27 µg/kg), benzofluoranthene (0.64 µg/kg). The legal limits (Reg. CE 1881/2006) were not exceeded in any plant.

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons µg/kg	1	2	3 ¹	4
Benzo(a)anthracene	0.95	-	0.25 0.36	-
Chrysene	0.97	-	0.27 0.43	-
Benzo(b)fluoranthene	0.64	-	-	-
Benzopyrene	0.70	-	- 0.79	-

Table 3. Residues of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons. 3¹: 2 values because of 2 different batch numbers

Microbiological examination

The microbiological examination was carried out for *Enterobacteriaceae*, mesophilic lactic acid bacteria, *Clostridium perfringens*, *Escherichia coli* and coagulase-positive staphylococci.

All microbiological parameters of plant no. 1 show a favorable outcome. In another plant, mesophilic lactic acid bacteria were below the value of 100 UFC/g, whereas in 2 others these

were 190.000.000 UFC/g, 220.000 UFC/g and 45.000.000 UFC/g respectively. *Enterobacteriaceae* were detected in the samples of 2 plants, registering a value of 220 UFC/g and 140.000 UFC/g. The results of the analysis of *Clostridia* and *E. coli* were always favorable. Coagulase positive staphylococci were detected in the fish fillets of 3 farms with values of 1000 UFC/g, 10.000 UFC/g and 100 UFC/g.

No samples exceed the legally permitted values (Reg. CE 2073/2005).

Microbiological examination UFC/g	1	2	3 ¹	4
<i>Enterobacteriaceae</i>	-	140,000	-	220,000
Mesophilic lactic acid bacteria	-	45,000,000	220,000	<100
			190,000,000	
<i>Clostridia perfringens</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>E. coli</i>	-	-	-	-
Coagulase positive staphylococci	-	<100	<10,000	<1,000

Table 4. Microbiological examination: 3¹: 2 values because of 2 different batch numbers

Listeria monocytogenes

Listeria was not detected in any sample.

Salmonella

No Salmonella spp. contamination was found in any sample.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION - SWITZERLAND

A total of 46 samples from 9 different species were taken:

Species	Number	At production site	In a store
Salmon	25	13	12
Trout	10	7	3
Herring	2	1	1
Mackerel	2		2
Char	2	2	
Tuna	2	1	1
Whitefish	1		1
Perch	1	1	
Pike-perch	1	1	20
Total	46	26	20

Table 5. Description of the samples

Chemical examination

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH)

25 PAHs were analyzed by Eurofins Scientific AG laboratory. The list is based on the recommendations of the EPA (Environmental Protection Agency, US) and the EU. All the 46 samples complied with the legislative requirements established in Switzerland ([RS 817.022.15](#)).

Artificial colorants and biogenic amines

All the analyses were carried out by the OFCO laboratory. No artificial colorants (Amaranth-E123; Azorubin-E122; Erythrosine-E127; Indigotine, indigo-E132; Orange yellow S-E110; Ponceau 4R-E124; Allura red AC-E129) were detected in any of the smoked fish tested.

As fish and fish products are foods likely to contain high levels of biogenic amines, they were investigated. Those were analysed: histamine, cadaverine, phenyléthylamine, putrescine, spermidine, spermine, Tyramine ([RS 817.024.1](#)).

All samples were compliant on the basis of chemical analysis: no colorants were detected; PAHs as well as histamine never exceeded the established legal standards ([RS 817.022.15](#); [RS 817.024.1](#)). For biogenic amines other than histamine, most values were below the limit of quantification, only a few values above 200 mg/kg were detected for tyramine and cadaverine in 5 samples.

The results of the chemical analyses did not reveal any non-conformity with the legal standards in force. Concerning the biogenic amines other than histamine, the values above 200 mg/kg show that for the samples concerned, production or storage were not always optimal, but without any consequences for the consumer. Concerning tyramine, considered together with histamine as the most toxic amines relevant for food safety (EFSA Panel on Biological Hazards 2011), the samples of the present study can be considered as low risk. Indeed, their results show maximum levels of tyramine well below the tolerable levels estimated at 950 mg/kg for fish (raw or processed), according to an Austrian study (Paulsen *et al.* 2012).

Microbiological examination

The following microbiological analysis parameters were taken into account and analyzed by the OFCO laboratory:

<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	Coagulase positive staphylococcus
<i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>Enterobacteriaceae</i>
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
Aerobic mesophilic bacteria	

Table 6. Microbiological parameters

7 out of 46 samples were considered non-compliant because they did not comply with legal requirements ([RS 817.024.1](#)) or good practice (Guidance Letter 2021/2). The non-conformities can be described as follows:

Sample	Aerobic mesophilic bacteria (CFU/g) ¹	Enterobacteriaceae (CFU/g) ²	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> ³	Smoking, and wood if known
Salmon (salt) #	37,000,000	-	-	Chestnut wood, temperature unknown
Salmon (salt, dextrose, antioxidant) #	37,000,000	-	-	Cold, (max 30°C), beech and oak wood
Whitefish (salt) #	25,000,000	-	-	Cold, temperature unknown
Trout (salt, pepper, whisky) *	-	>49,000	-	Cold between 18°C and 23°C
Salmon with herbs (salt, sugar, parsley, chives) *	>49,000,000	>49,000	-	Cold (24°C, 2-3h), cherry wood
Salmon (salt, sugar, pepper) *	-	>49,000	detected in 25g	Cold (24°C, 2-3h) cherry wood
Salmon (salt, sugar, spices) *	-	-	detected in 25g	Cold (max. 25°C, 6h), beech wood

Table 7. Details of non-compliant samples. * taken at the production site; # taken in a store; - in compliance with the legislation.

No non-compliance was found for the remaining microbiological parameters: *Salmonella* spp. *Clostridium perfringens*, coagulase positive Staphylococci and *Escherichia coli*.

The analyses carried out confirm that smoked fish is a foodstuff at risk for the consumer, particularly from a microbiological point of view. Indeed, 7 samples out of 46 were contested as to their microbiological quality, of which 2 samples were contaminated with *Listeria monocytogenes*. It was not possible to determine whether the presence of these bacteria was due to the processing and handling of the fish or to other added ingredients (spices, herbs, etc.). On-site inspections of the companies responsible showed that the *Listeria monocytogenes* parameter was not taken into account in their self-supervision system (mandatory practice in Switzerland ([RS 817.0](#))). The companies concerned have since complied.

In order to produce smoked fish of a sanitary quality, the fight against spoilage flora and against *L. monocytogenes* must be carried out at two levels: within the company, through compliance with good hygiene and cleaning-disinfection practices, and in the finished

¹ [Guidance Letter 2021/2.1](#), indicative value: 10'000'000 CFU/g

² [Guidance Letter 2021/2.1](#): indicative value: 10'000 CFU/g

³ [Ordinance on hygiene in food-related activities](#), safety criteria: Not detectable in 25 g

product, through controlled salting and smoking and maintenance of the cold chain below +4°C until the consumer receives it. Of the 6 establishments (artisanal fisheries and super-market fish shops) inspected, only 3 had a concept of self-supervision including the *Listeria monocytogenes* parameter and its monitoring.

CONCLUSION

The results of the analyses of the products in the South Tyrolean farms showed that they were all in compliance from a microbiological point of view. However, in terms of chemical parameters, residues of disinfectants were detected in these samples taken at the end of production. Further study will be necessary to determine the origin of these residues and to clarify the sanitation methods of the working surfaces.

In Switzerland, all the results were in conformity with the chemical parameters (note that testing for disinfectants was not performed). On the other hand, 7 samples - of which 4 were taken on site at the end of the production process - out of 46 were considered as not compliant with the legal requirements on hygiene. Even if the sampling of the present study is not representative of the whole of Switzerland, the results corroborate the fact that smoked fish can present a risk for the consumer at microbiological levels, particularly with regard to *Listeria monocytogenes* (2 contaminated samples). This element must absolutely be taken into account in the implementation of self-supervision at the smoking and/or packaging company of smoked fish.

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